

Artificial Intelligence for Smartphone Imaging of the External Eye: A Scoping Review

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Background. Anterior-segment disorders, particularly uncorrected refractive error and cataract, account for most global visual impairment, yet the bulk of ophthalmic-AI research focuses on retinal disease.

Objective. To map published studies that apply artificial intelligence to smartphone images of the external or anterior eye, summarising target conditions, reported performance and clinical maturity.

Methods. A scoping review followed PRISMA-ScR and the JBI Manual. MEDLINE, Embase, Scopus and ClinicalTrials.gov were searched from January 2008 to May 2025 using a strategy co-developed with information specialists at the International Centre for Eye Health, LSHTM. Two reviewers independently screened and charted records.

Results. Thirty-three studies from sixteen countries met the criteria; sixty-nine per cent originated in low- and middle-income settings. Keratitis, cataract and strabismus were the most frequent targets. The median cohort size was 495 participants (range 12–7,726) with 43,379 images analysed. Prospective image acquisition was reported in seventy-three per cent of studies. Twenty-four studies developed and internally validated new models, nine externally validated existing models and one evaluated feasibility in practice. Reported area-under-the-curve values ranged from 0.83 to 1.00, while sensitivity and specificity each ranged from 0.25 to 1.00.

Conclusion. Research on smartphone-based AI for external-eye disease is growing but remains early stage. Larger, more diverse smartphone datasets, multicentre external validation, standardised reporting and implementation trials are needed to establish real-world effectiveness.

1 Introduction

An estimated **1.2 billion** people are currently living with near- or distance-visual impairment; projections indicate this will rise to **1.7 billion** by 2050. The burden is greatest in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where specialist ophthalmic services are scarce [1]. Globally, the leading causes of sight-loss are anterior-segment disorders, notably uncorrected refractive error and cataract, yet most ophthalmic-AI research has concentrated on retinal disease [2,3].

Smartphone health tools are helping to close this gap. Peek Vision is an mHealth organisation that enables non-specialists to carry out simple eye examinations in schools and communities, identify people with unmet need and connect them to care. Peek-powered programmes have already screened more than 13 million people and connected 1.4 million to care [4]. Standard smartphones capture diagnostic-quality images of the external eye, and combining these images with automated analysis offers a scalable route to detect anterior-segment disease in community settings.

We performed a scoping review to map the international evidence on artificial-intelligence systems that analyse smartphone images of the external or anterior eye, summarising target conditions, technical performance and clinical maturity.

2 Methods

2.1 Protocol & Reporting Framework

The review followed *PRISMA-ScR* and the *JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis* [5,6].

2.2 Search Strategy Development

ICEH information specialists co-designed a Boolean strategy with three blocks: 1. **Mobile device terms** (“smartphone”, “tablet”); 2. **External-eye disease/sign terms** (ICD-10 anterior-segment codes plus keywords such as “red eye”, “corneal opacity”, “eyelid mass”); 3. **AI terms** (“machine learning”, “deep learning”, “convolutional neural network”). Searches ran in MEDLINE, Embase, Scopus and ClinicalTrials.gov (1 Jan 2008–31 May 2025) with no language limits; non-English records were translated.

2.3 Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion — peer-reviewed human studies applying AI to smartphone/tablet images or video of the external/anterior eye at any lifecycle stage.

Exclusion — posterior-segment imaging, systemic-disease detection, non-clinical tasks.

2.4 Selection & Data Charting

Two reviewers screened titles/abstracts and full text. Data extracted: country, design, setting, demographics, imaging hardware/protocol, dataset provenance, AI architecture, validation, reference standard and metrics; disagreements resolved by a third reviewer.

3 Results

3.1 Study Volume & Geography

Of 1,609 records, 33 met inclusion (Fig. 1). Studies spanned 16 countries, with 69 % from LMICs; China ($n = 11$) and India ($n = 8$) contributed the most publications (Fig. 2). All papers were published between 2018 and 2025.

3.2 Conditions Investigated

The commonest targets were keratitis ($n = 8$), cataract ($n = 6$) and strabismus ($n = 5$). Other conditions included primary angle-closure glaucoma, corneal scarring, blepharoptosis, leukocoria and ocular-surface tumours.

3.3 Participants & Image Volumes

Twenty-seven studies reported cohort size, totalling 29,462 participants (median 495; range 12–7 726). Twenty reported image counts, giving 43,379 images; the median image-to-participant ratio was 2.47 (range 0.5–52). Of 21 studies reporting age group, 42.85 % focused on adults, 38.09 % on paediatrics and 19.06 % included both. Sex distribution was stated in 53 %; ethnicity in 12 %.

3.4 Image Capture Protocols

Prospective imaging was used by 24/33 (73 %) studies. Recruitment sites were mainly hospital eye clinics (82 %); others included schools, private clinics, home visits and online databases. Smartphone cameras alone were employed in 31 studies; two studies added attachments (a hand-held non-mydratic fundus camera and a mini slit-lamp). Acquisition parameters (distance, lighting, positioning, flash) were documented in 85 %; flash was used in 58 %. The smartphone model was specified in 82 %.

3.5 AI Development & Validation

External validation: 9 studies (27 %) tested an existing model on new smartphone data. New models: 24 studies (73 %) developed and internally validated an algorithm. Of these, 60.9 % trained and validated solely on smartphone images, 21.7 % trained on non-smartphone images and tested on smartphone data, and 17.4 % used mixed sources. Only one study progressed to feasibility testing in everyday care.

3.6 Reference Standards & Performance

In 58 % of studies the reference standard was a clinical diagnosis; the remainder used expert image grading alone. AUC was reported in 17 studies (0.83–1.00). Sensitivity and specificity, available for 22 studies, each ranged 0.25–1.00. Other metrics (F1, PPV, NPV, Cohen’s κ , IoU, Jaccard, Hausdorff) were inconsistently reported. Figure 3 plots sensitivity vs. specificity by condition cluster; two studies with values outside the plotted range are omitted for clarity.

4 Discussion & Conclusion

Smartphone-based AI for anterior-segment disease is expanding, especially for keratitis, cataract and strabismus in LMICs. Nevertheless, most studies remain at the validation stage, and heterogeneity in imaging protocols, datasets and reporting standards limits generalisability.

Future research priorities

- Build large, demographically diverse smartphone datasets covering multiple devices and imaging conditions.
- Conduct external multicentre validation and head-to-head comparisons with existing care pathways.
- Adopt transparent, standardised reporting of imaging hardware, acquisition parameters and AI metrics (for example, CONSORT-AI and STARD-AI when published) [7,8].
- Run implementation trials that measure accuracy, cost-effectiveness and equity impact in community and primary-care settings.

Addressing these gaps is essential before smartphone-AI tools can safely enhance early detection of anterior-segment disease and reduce avoidable blindness worldwide.

Table 1. Condition clusters and frequency of mentions (total $n = 51$ across 32 studies). *Refractive-error cluster includes “Visual impairment”.

Cluster	Mentions	Break-down (condition → count)
Amblyopia & Strabismus	9	Strabismus 5; Amblyopia risk factors 4
Keratitis	8	Infectious 4; Immunological 2; Unspecified 2
Ocular-surface disease & tumours	8	Tumour 2; Ocular-surface disease 2; Pterygium 2; Conj. melanoma 1; Dry-eye 1
Corneal sequelae / degeneration	6	Scarring 2; Deposition 2; Bullous keratopathy 2
Lens opacity	6	Cataract 6
Refractive error*	6	Refractive error 2; Myopia 2; Anisometropia 1; Visual impairment 1
Glaucoma	2	Primary angle-closure glaucoma 2
Orbit / adnexa	3	Thyroid-eye disease 1; Ptosis 1; Blepharoptosis 1
Neuro-motility disorders	2	Nystagmus 1; Nerve palsy 1
Leukocoria	1	Leukocoria 1

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Fig. 1. PRISMA flow diagram of study selection.

Fig. 2. Global distribution of the 33 included studies. Dark blue: 8–12; medium blue: 4–7; light blue: <4.

Fig. 3. Sensitivity vs. specificity by eye-condition cluster. Points colour-coded by the ten clusters in Table 1. Two outliers are excluded for clarity.